

IMPROVING THE DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM LOAD FORECASTING OF URBAN CONGESTION AREAS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: *Power system is paramount important to drive development and industrialization. Every day, both residential and commercial areas yearn for improved power to drive their day-to-day running of their business. In already congested areas, many buildings are demolished and towers are erected. Simple industrial machines are phased out and replaced with heavy industrial machines. The increase in load exceeds the capacity of the distribution transformer and the distribution substation capacity. These problems cannot be handled by short-term, midterm, or long-term load forecasting techniques only, due to innovation or fast development in already urban, congested areas. These uncontrolled practices led to the burning of power transformers, distribution transformers, incessant faults, and unwanted outages and frequent load shedding. These affected many businesses and caused psychological trauma to residential customers. A hybrid technique embedded with artificial intelligence was modeled to mitigate the incessant load shedding, especially during the peak period, and reduce burning of power facility. The hybrid technique was modeled and infused into First Power Distribution network which interface with the indoor panel. The technique predict futuristic load and characterize the load before introduction into the network. When the load introduction exceeds the carrying capacity, it will trigger the circuit breaker to trip automatically. Before the hybrid technique embedded with artificial intelligence, the outage rate is 50 percent but with the technique embedded with artificial intelligence. The force outage rate was reduced to 15 percent.*

Keywords: *Artificial, Distribution, Forecasting, Intelligence, Load*

1. Introduction

The power system network is dynamic in nature, there is increasing demand in power supply because of multi-use of power system in the areas of research institute, hospital and surgery operation, agricultural production and preservation, industries and production process, etc. The multi uses of power accelerate the high demand of power supply. In the developed country, steady, available and affordable power supply is attainable. But in under developed or developing country like Nigeria, steady, available and affordable power supply is nightmare which mar industrial development and lagging in infrastructural development. It is a disappointment that the availability of power supply is not sufficient enough, yet, it was discovered that the available power facilities are obsolete; they cannot withstand the carrying capacity due to aging of power facilities. However, there is low investment in power sector, to boost the power supply. Even with the decentralization of the power authorities, unbundling of transmission company of Nigeria, lack of fund, corruptions and energy theft have discourage investor from investing in power sector and improve availability of power supply. The epileptic power supply met with serious constraint due to growing power demand attributed to growing population, expansion of industries without the corresponding increase in power availability, increase in power facilities and increase in carrying capacities to match the growing need and power demand. These problems led to congestion or disruption of power availability, especially in the urban areas where the demand for power availability is more. This give birth to load shedding of feeders from distribution substation and local transformer load shedding which is not healthy for both residential customers and commercial customers. These constraints is taken care by power engineers when designing a power layout of a location. They consider the futuristic demand of the power demand by providing extra feeders, extra unit and proper documentation of new customers to ascertain if the allowable capacities of the transformer or the feeder can carry the load. In some certain cases, the load introduced into the network is beyond the carrying capacity of the distribution transformer and the feeder. Forecasting can be short time, that is considering the daily load or the peak load over a period of time, and longtime forecasting, where the seasonal and number years are taking into consideration. Artificial intelligence was deployed to manage the daily peak load and ensure that only the allowable load and carrying capacities is introduced into the networks. First Power distribution network was used and artificial intelligence incorporated into the system and matches the load with the carrying capacity.

2. Literature Review

Load forecasting can be short term, midterm or long term, shaving peak load or fluctuating load is a strategy for mitigation of load in transmission or distribution line [Zeinab 2024]. The results showed that neural network shed load during peak which reduce force outage but it didn't predict the possible peak load but isolate when the peak load is violated.

Short term load forecasting is important in power system because it takes care of daily peak load[Jiam 2020] .He presented an algorithm of predicting the peak load without mitigation.

Atla[2025], presented Load forecasting and methods of calculating load forecasting without presenting practical approach of load mitigations during peak load.

Hadri etal[2019] , presented smart load forecasting approach , the algorithm will be able to predict the load for the smart building but cannot predict the load of the network or the geographical areas under coverage.

Ifeagwu [2024], presented efficient power outage solution using independent solar generator but the study cannot predict the growing need of power demand in Nigeria power system network.

Ugwu [2021], presented real time technique of mitigating outages in transmission line but the study didn't present an algorithm for load forecasting.

Hasan etal[2025] presented a new approach of predicting the load in transmission, and distribution system using renewable energy sources but the study failed to address the mitigating steps when the peak load is exceeding the plant capacity or power transformer capacities, which is the problem this paper want to address. To use artificial intelligence to predict future load and ensure that the peak load does not exceed the capacity of the transformer.

3. Methodology.

The method employed in this work is empirical and analytical approached. First Power Distribution network was used for the test system. Specifically, Fegge Injection Substation was used which consists of Bida Feeder, Uga Feeder, Market Feeder, and Fegge Feeder.

Hybrid technique embedded with artificial intelligence was modeled to mitigate the incessant load shedding, and reduce burning of power facility. The hybrid and artificial intelligence system was interface with personal computer and the data updated in real time. Before load is introduce to any distribution transformer or any of the feeders, the load capacities of the machine is clamp using clamp meter and the data feed into the personal computer, once the load exceed the capacities of the transformer, it will trip that particular feeder off automatically. The system also forecast the increase in load during peak period and determines if the feeder or the distribution can withstand the load during peak or seasonal peak even if the data is feed during off peak period.

Mathematically

Using thyristor equation

Thyristor $T =$ Carrying Capacity C 1

$T = X_L \alpha$ 2

Since $T = C$, then, $C = X_L \alpha$ 3

Where X_L is the power flow $= V I \cos \theta$ 4

α = artificial intelligence

Load forecasting formular = $V \cos\theta \times \alpha$ 5

Fig

1; Hybrid at abnormal condition

The fig 1 showed the output result of hybrid embedded with artificial intelligence at abnormal condition. It showed that the load exceeded the carrying capacity.

Fig 2; Hybrid at normal condition

The fig 2 showed the output result of hybrid embedded with artificial intelligence at normal condition. It showed that the load did not exceed the carrying capacity.

4. Results

The hybrid technique was modeled with embedded artificial intelligence and interface with personal computer. The First Power Distribution Company Injection Sub was used, which is Fegge Injection Sub Station, with capacity of 1 × 7.5MVA and 1 × 15MVA. With 33KV Incoming and four 11KV out going feeders, which include Bida with carrying capacity of 250amp, Uga with carrying capacity of 150amp, Market with carrying capacity of 300amp and Fegge with carrying capacity of 130amp. From the simulation, when the load of each is below the carrying capacity, it allow the power flow, but when it

exceed the carrying capacities, like in Bida, 400amp, Uga, 230amp, Market, 450amp, and Fegge, 150amp, it display red, in the personal computer, which shows danger, it will trigger the circuit to open the breaker until the right load is maintain, before trial reclosure is done.

Fig 3; Peak load at normal condition

The fig 3 showed that Bida, Uga, Market and Fegge are within the carrying capacities, the personal computer interface with the hybrid embedded with artificial intelligence will show blue as shown in fig 2, it will allow supply to flow and inject power out.

Fig 4; Peak load at abnormal

The fig 4 showed that Bida, Uga, Market and Fegge are above the carrying capacities, the personal computer interface with the hybrid embedded with artificial intelligence will show red as shown in fig 1, it will trigger the circuit breaker to open and stop power flow until the anomaly is corrected and trial reclosure is made.

5. Conclusion

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The study explore forecasting technique in mitigating frequent load shedding in distribution system as a result of urban population growth and industrialization. As the quest of power increase, and population increase, which led to erection of new buildings, and increase power usage, taking capacities grow beyond the transformer rated capacity or feeder carrying capacities, which resulted to the feeder tripping on over load and distribution transformer blowing off. The tripping is more pronounced during the peak load which normally occurred between 6 am to 7 am in the morning and 6pm to 9pm in the night for residential customers. For commercial customers, the peak load occurred between 11 am to 5 pm. During this period, the distribution transformers blow off due to overload and the feeders in the distribution substation tripped on over load, and will be restore back during off peak period. This scenarios affected both residential and commercial customers. Artificial intelligence was incorporated with the system, which calculate the incoming load and match it with the capacity of the feeders and the transformers, to ensure it does not tripped even during peak period. This approached reduce forced outage to 15 percent and improve operational efficiency based on the simulated data using First Power Distribution networks.

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